

ON THE BALAKRISHNAN'S FORMULA FOR THE FRACTIONAL POWER OF A MATRIX

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Abstract:

We know that the resolvent of a matrix $A_{n \times n}$ is the Laplace transform of $\exp(tA)$, which allow us to give an elementary deduction of Balakrishnan's formula for the fractional power of a matrix.

Key Words: Matrix Exponential Function, Laplace Transform, Gamma Function, Sylvester's Formula, Balakrishnan's Expression.

1. Introduction:

In [1] we can see the Balakrishnan's formula [2] for the fractional power of a matrix $A_{n \times n}$:

$$A^\alpha = \frac{1}{\pi} \text{Sin}(\pi\alpha) A \int_0^\infty s^{\alpha-1} \frac{1}{sI+A} ds, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, we know the following relation [3] involving the Laplace transform [4] of matrix exponential function [5]:

$$\mathcal{L}[e^{-tA}] = \frac{1}{sI+A} = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} e^{-tA} dt. \quad (2)$$

In Sec. 2 we use (2) to show an elementary deduction of (1), and to make an application of it to a two-dimensional matrix for $\alpha = 1/2$, and the result is compared with the corresponding expression given by the Sylvester's formula [6, 7].

2. Balakrishnan's Expression:

From (2) it is immediate that:

$$A \int_0^\infty \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{sI+A} ds = \int_0^\infty A e^{-tA} dt \int_0^\infty e^{-st} s^{\alpha-1} ds = \Gamma(\alpha) \int_0^\infty A e^{-tA} t^{-\alpha} dt = \Gamma(\alpha) \Gamma(1-\alpha) A^\alpha, \quad (3)$$

Involving the gamma function [8, 9] verifying the reflection property:

$$\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(1-\alpha) = \frac{\pi}{\text{Sin}(\pi\alpha)}, \quad (4)$$

Then (3) and (4) imply (1), *q.e.d.*

Now we apply (1) to the matrix:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A^2 = -I, \quad \lambda_1 = -\lambda_2 = i, \quad (5)$$

Therefore:

$$e^{-tA} = \text{Cos } t \cdot I - \text{Sin } t \cdot A, \quad \mathcal{L}[e^{-tA}] = \frac{1}{s^2+1} (sI - A), \quad (6)$$

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{sI+A} ds = I \int_0^\infty \frac{s^\alpha}{s^2+1} ds - A \int_0^\infty \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^2+1} ds = \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\text{Cos}(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2})} I - \frac{1}{\text{Sin}(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2})} A \right],$$

Hence the Balakrishnan's formula (1) gives the fractional power:

$$A^\alpha = \text{Cos} \left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2} \right) \cdot I + \text{Sin} \left(\frac{\pi\alpha}{2} \right) \cdot A, \quad (7)$$

And in particular for $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$:

$$A^{1/2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

On the other hand, Sylvester [6,7, 10-12] obtained the following interpolating definition of $f(A)$:

$$f(A) = \sum_{j=1}^n f(\lambda_j) \prod_{k \neq j} \frac{A - \lambda_k I}{\lambda_j - \lambda_k}, \quad (9)$$

Which is valid if all eigen values are different from each other. Buchheim [13] generalized (9) to multiple proper values using Hermite interpolation, thereby giving the first completely general definition of a matrix function. We can employ (9) with $f(A) = A^{1/2}$ for the matrix (5) to obtain the value:

$$A^{1/2} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

Which is different to (8), however, both results verify the property $A^{1/2} A^{1/2} = A$.

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